

SMART ERA

EVALUATION PUBLIC SUMMARY REPORT

SMART ERA

1st Open Call for Pilots Add-ons

Authors: FBA/FBC

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Project acronym: **SMART ERA**

Project grant agreement number: **101084160**

Project full name: **SMART community-led transition for Europe's Rural Areas**

SMART ERA 1st Open Call for Pilots Add-ons information

The Open Call was opened on the 28th August 2025.

It was closed on 4th November 2025 at 15:00 CET.

The call was published at the SMART ERA Website (<https://smartera-project.eu/>) and on the Horizon Europe Participants Portal.

Full call details were published at: <https://opportunities.getonepass.eu/applications/smart-era/start>

Number of proposals received and selected for financial support

The evaluation and selection have been completed.

All applicants have been informed about the evaluation results for their proposal for financial support.

The submitted proposals passed through various stages:

- **250** submitted
- **225** eligible
- **88** passed pre-scoring threshold and moved to expert evaluation phase
- **69** scored above threshold in the expert evaluation
- **33** top-scored (top 3 per challenge) projects were invited to Pitching Days
- **11** projects were pre-selected for funding (1 per challenge) and 15 for the reserve list

Proposals selected

	PROJECT ACRONYM	ORGANIZATION LEGAL NAME	COUNTRY	AMOUNT AWARDED
CH#1	MUU-CHAIN	ITC - Innovation Technology Cluster / Inovacijsko tehnološki grozd	Slovenia	60,000.0€
CH#2	SAGE	Regrowth	Italy	60,000.0€
CH#3	SAVIA	IURBAN DIGITAL TOURISM S.L.	Spain	60,000.0€
CH#4	NeuroFarming	Eight Bells Ltd. (8BELLS)	Cyprus	60,000.0€
CH#5	LocalTrustLink	BINARE Oy	Finland	60,000.0€
CH#6	TAIKA-RC	Midnight Forge Oy (Virtual Dawn is registered brand name)	Finland	60,000.0€
CH#7	SAT	Saakuru technologijos, UAB	Lithuania	60,000.0€
CH#8	SMART-HERZ	Positive d.o.o. Novi Sad	Serbia	60,000.0€
CH#9	ToyotaGo 3.0	Toyota Adria d.o.o.	Slovenia	60,000.0€
CH#10	RuralMed-AI	SYNDESIS LTD RESEARCH AND INNOVATION in Healthcare	Greece	60,000.0€
CH#11	Travel2Devetaki	TRAVEL2FIT PRIVATE COMPANY	Greece	60,000.0€

Challenge #1: Information system for tracing agrifood production (Val di Sole)

Challenge #2: Information system for Pasture ecosystem monitoring (Val di Sole)

Challenge #3: AI Chatbot for personalized touristic experience (Sóller/Tramuntana)

Challenge #4: AI tool for micro-farming management (Sóller/Tramuntana)

Challenge #5: SMART Economy Service Platform (Northern Ostrobothnia)

Challenge #6: AI-Assisted Conceptualization of Rural Businesses Based on Deep Local Knowledge (Northern Ostrobothnia)

Challenge #7: Smart B2B platform for the agro-tourism sector (East Herzegovina)

Challenge #8: SMART platform for personalized tourism experience (East Herzegovina)

Challenge #9: Mobile App for mobility on demand (Šmarje-Padna)

Challenge #10: AI GP Support System (Devetaki Plateau)

Challenge #11: Map-based digital platform for tourist information, promotion and tailor made trips (Devetaki Plateau)

